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PRESILIENT

Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

Comparative Horizon Scanning Report

Informality and innovation: building post-pandemic resilient communities in Chile.

Sara Mengato

Dublin City University

School of Law and Government

sara.mengato2@mail.dcu.ie

A23275476

Executive Summary

This country report forms part of the PRESILIENT project's Horizon Scanning (HS) activity, which aim was to identify the economic sectors in Chile most impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic and those demonstrating potential for adaptation, innovation, and recovery, particularly within the context of informality. Chile's economy, characterised by high urban informality, uneven digital access, and a strong service sector orientation, was significantly affected by the pandemic-induced economic shock.

This Chile-focused HS report draws on a qualitative, desk-based methodology that includes academic and policy papers as well as media and grey literature. The analytical approach is drawn from sociology and political economy, with an emphasis on interpreting sectoral trends through socio-economic and behavioural lenses.

The findings reveal that urban formal and informal sectors such as tourism, hospitality, commerce, and transportation were among the hardest hit, primarily due to mobility restrictions, lockdowns, and declining consumer demand. In contrast, digital-oriented sectors such as e-commerce, telecommunications, and food delivery services experienced rapid growth, driven by technological innovation, behavioural shifts, and state-promoted digital adaptation. This sector also puts Chile post-pandemic economy in regional and global comparison providing an insightful outlook on Chile's economic potential to adapt and recover from economic crisis.

By mapping both vulnerability and innovation, this report contributes to understanding the evolving dynamics of Chile's economy in the wake of COVID-19. It underscores the need for inclusive policy frameworks that address digital divides, support informal workers, and harness local innovation to build equitable and resilient futures.

Keywords

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Chilean Economy; Macroeconomic stability; Economic growth; Privatization; Competitiveness; International trade liberalization; Global Value Chains; Economic polarization; Political disenchantment; Post-pandemic recovery; Poverty; Emigration; Inequalities; Informal economy; Extractivism; Organized crime; Political and social uncertainties; Corruption; Violence; NAFTA.

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Introduction

This document is part of the PRESILIENT project's WP1 deliverables and presents the Chilean contribution to the Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise. The HS methodology, outlined in the PRESILIENT Global Research Protocol, is designed to identify early signals, structural risks, and opportunities for innovation that shape the evolving landscape of informal economies in the Global South. The central objective is to trace which sectors declined or adapted in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, with particular attention to those capable of fostering more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable post-pandemic futures.

In Chile, the HS exercise was carried out through a qualitative, interpretive approach grounded in critical development studies and informed by feminist political economic theories. In line with the shared methodology, the report draws on approximately 150 curated sources, including academic literature, media, grey literature, and policy documents. Rather than solely relying on statistical or automated trend mapping, the analysis foregrounds local debates along with statistics from governmental and non-governmental organizations, which includes to understand how crisis and recovery are experienced on the ground and from several viewpoints.

- A comprehensive review of academic literature, policy reports, and international assessments related to informality, urban governance, and post-pandemic recovery in Chile and Latin America;
- Analysis of grey literature, including government documents, NGO reports, and multilateral publications focused on informal economies and informal sectors
- A comparative reading of local and national media debates, particularly concerning community mobilizations, social inequality, pandemic governance, and contested urban policies;

The research highlights the disproportionate impact of the pandemic on service-based and high informal sectors such as tourism, hospitality, transportation, and small retail, particularly in urban informal economies. Informal workers in these areas faced acute disruptions in income and access to basic infrastructure, income opportunities and housing. By contrast, digitally enabled sectors such as e-commerce, telecommunications, and food delivery expanded rapidly, often formalizing through platforms yet deepening precarity in new ways. Workers in informal jobs, especially the most economically vulnerable groups, have developed complex survival strategies across fragmented urban geographies, navigating limited mobility, state invisibility, and extractive urban governance.

These Chilean insights reinforce a broader PRESILIENT argument: that informality should not be viewed as a problem to be solved by formalization alone, but rather as a terrain of resilience, and political agency. The findings also point to the need for situated and localized analysis and policy recommendations that recognize and support the practices of informal actors without undermining their autonomy or criminalizing them.

This report will inform the next phases of the PRESILIENT project, including the Delphi Survey and case study development, and will contribute to a forthcoming EU policy brief on informal work and housing in Valparaiso, Chile.

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Methodological Note on Data Collection and Processing

This report follows the standard research protocol defined by the PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning (HS) framework. While qualitative and interpretive in orientation, the exercise also employed a structured approach to ensure cross-country comparability. Data collection relied on pre-defined keywords related to informality, economic recovery, and resilience. Following the shared methodological guidelines, the Chilean HS study drew on a structured corpus of approximately 150 sources—comprising 50 academic publications, 50 media articles, and 50 grey literature or policy documents.

These materials were identified through targeted keyword searches in both Spanish and English, selected for relevance, and critically analysed using the researcher’s contextual knowledge of Chile’s socio-political and economic realities. The process involved iterative keyword refinement, triangulation across different types of sources, and the inclusion of independent and community-based media to reflect underrepresented perspectives. Each step, from keyword development to report drafting, was carried out in alignment with PRESILIENT’s epistemological commitment to qualitative depth, methodological transparency, and critical engagement.

Informal Economies in Chile: Socioeconomic Context

Chile is a highly urbanized, middle-income country characterized by a dual economy marked by strong macroeconomic institutions on one hand, and extensive informal labour and housing on the other. Despite its reputation for market liberalism and digital innovation, informal employment accounts for over 27% of the workforce nationally, with higher rates among women, youth, and migrants. Informality is particularly pronounced in urban peripheries and in economic sectors such as commerce, transportation, domestic work, and street vending. Key sectors such as tourism, retail trade, transportation, and hospitality, were among the hardest hit by lockdown measures, curfews, and prolonged school and workplace closures.

Chile’s informal economy is shaped by multiple intersecting factors: the residual nature of welfare policies, neoliberal urban governance, rising cost of living, and increasing migration. The pandemic deepened these pressures, exposing how fragile state protections are for informal workers. Despite digital innovations in some areas, many informal workers, especially those in retail, domestic service, or street-dependent sectors—were unable to adapt to digital modes of work or income generation. Yet, informal economies also revealed important capacities for resilience, including mutual aid networks, digital micro-enterprises, and community self-organization, such as the return of *ollas communes* (communal kitchens).

Regional and Global Comparison

Chile’s experience during the COVID-19 pandemic aligns with broader trends across Latin America and the Global South. Like Brazil, Ecuador, Colombia, and Mexico, Chile saw steep contractions in service-oriented sectors such as tourism, retail, and transport. These shared vulnerabilities

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reflected the region's reliance on informal labour in contact-intensive and low-regulation sectors, many of which operate without safety nets or worker protections.

In contrast, Chile's rapid digital uptake in sectors like e-commerce, telecommunications, and platform-based food delivery paralleled developments in Colombia, Vietnam, and Kenya. The shift to digital platforms was driven by behavioural change and public policies promoting technological innovation. However, this transition was uneven and often reinforced new forms of precarity, particularly for gig workers subject to algorithmic management, low pay, and lack of benefits. Unlike Vietnam or Brazil, where digital ecosystems have stronger integration with informal actors, in Chile platform expansion did not always translate into meaningful inclusion or improved working conditions.

Chile's small-scale agriculture showed relative resilience during the crisis, a pattern also seen in Colombia and Mexico. By contrast, countries like Morocco, more affected by environmental shocks such as drought, experienced deeper disruptions in rural livelihoods. Chile benefited from relatively favourable climatic conditions during the pandemic years, allowing agricultural production and distribution to remain more stable.

In sum, Chile's trajectory illustrates both the shared pressures and distinct conditions shaping informal economies across the Global South. While the country's digital transition and urban resilience strategies offer potential lessons, persistent structural inequalities overlook the need for a more inclusive and territorially grounded approach to post-pandemic recovery.

Emerging Trends and Feedback

In the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, Chile's informal economy has been marked by uneven recovery and adaptation. While sectors such as tourism, hospitality, and transportation were severely impacted by lockdowns and mobility restrictions, others, particularly e-commerce, telecommunications, and food delivery, grew rapidly. The sectors that flourished during the pandemic, such as e-commerce, telecommunications, and food delivery, are expected to maintain stable growth. The normalization of remote work, hybrid learning, and digital public services has embedded these technologies into daily routines and institutional frameworks. This transformation has not only driven economic productivity but also reshaped cultural and consumer practices. However, these gains remain uneven across social and territorial lines, particularly for informal workers excluded from digital transitions. Going forward, Chile's recovery will be shaped not only by macroeconomic growth but by how effectively policies engage with the structural divides that determine who benefits from these emerging trends.

Related Outputs and Publications

This national report is part of the broader Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise developed within the PRESILIENT project. The following outputs have been produced from this collective research:

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- Molina, J. L., Pulgar Corrotea, M., Polese, A., Fradejas-García, I., Ianole-Călin, R., Isaev, A., Mengato, S., Nguyen, M., Carracedo, D., De Lombaerde, G., Avesani, M., Sasikornwong, N., Gambardella, M., Andrias, B., Massera, M., Lima, J. P., Cisagara, B., Rahman, A., Kabaghe, W., & D'Urso, D. (2024). *PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning Dataset [Data set]*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285318>

This dataset is the consolidated output of the Horizon Scanning research conducted across 15 countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (including Chile). It comprises three corpora of references: academic literature, media articles, and grey literature sources, gathered and curated to explore economic transformations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on informal economies.

- Fradejas García, I., Pulgar, M., Molina, J. L., Ianole-Călin, R., & Polese, A. (2024). *Volatility, growth, decline and sustainability perspective of domestic economic sectors after the pandemic: A comparative Horizon Scanning of 15 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273561>

This comparative publication presents the aggregate results of the Horizon Scanning exercise conducted in 15 countries. Using a keyword-based supervised topic detection method across the combined corpora, it provides an overview of post-pandemic trends, highlighting convergences and divergences among countries and across types of sources. It also discusses patterns of economic volatility, recovery, and the sustainability of growth trajectories in the informal sector.

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